

Synthesis, characterization and biological screening of some new aryloxyacetic acid analogs

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Abstract : A novel series of 2-(4-bromo-2-formyl-phenoxy)acetyl amino acid and peptide analogs was synthesized by the coupling of 2-(4-bromo-2-formyl-phenoxy)acetic acid with different amino acid methyl ester hydrochlorides, dipeptide and tripeptide methyl esters using dicyclohexylcarbodiimide as the coupling agent and N-methylmorpholine as the base. Structures of all the newly synthesized compounds were elucidated on basis of IR, NMR and MS spectral data as well as elemental analysis. On pharmacological screening, some peptide derivatives were found to exhibit potent bioactivity against gram-negative bacterium *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, pathogenic fungus *Candida albicans* and earthworms *Megascolex konkanensis*, *Pontoscotex corethruses* and *Eudrilus* sp. Dermatophytes were found to be moderately sensitive towards the newly synthesized analogs. Hydrolyzed peptide derivatives displayed better antimicrobial activity in comparison to corresponding esters.

Keywords : 5-Bromosalicylaldehyde, aryloxyacetic acid, peptide, coupling, biological activity.

Introduction

Aryloxyacetic acid derivatives are known to possess a variety of pharmacological activities such as antibacterial¹, anti-inflammatory and analgesic^{2,3}, antisickling⁴, antilipaemic and antiplatelet^{5,6}, diuretic⁷ and inhibitory activity of cathepsin K and aldose reductase^{8,9}. Besides it, literature has proved that incorporation of amino acids/peptides into the heterocyclic moieties have yielded bioactive analogs with fewer side effects^{10,11}. Therefore, keeping in view the biological potency of aryloxyacetic acids as well as taking advantage of biodegradability and biocompatibility of peptides and further, in continuation of our work on synthesizing potent aromatic/hetero-aromatic analogs of amino acids and peptides¹², a series of novel amino acid/peptide analogs of 2-(4-bromo-2-formyl-phenoxy)acetic acid was synthesized with an anticipation to get compounds with more therapeutic efficacy.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of 2-(4-bromo-2-formyl-phenoxy)acetic acid **1** was accomplished with good yield (>75%). Presence of free carboxylic group in compound **1** was clearly indicated by singlets at 172.9 and 7.05 ppm corresponding to carbonyl and hydroxyl portions of -COOH group in ¹³C

and ¹H NMR spectra. Prior to coupling, boc-di/tripeptide methyl esters were deprotected at amino terminal and their structures were confirmed by disappearance of singlet at 1.55 ppm (for nine protons of butyl-t) in ¹H NMR spectra and singlets at 157.5, 79.9, 28.8 ppm (for five carbons of boc) in ¹³C NMR spectra of tripeptide methyl esters. All aryloxyacetic acid derivatives **1**₁₋₁₂ were synthesized successfully and DCC was found to be a good coupling agent providing 67–84% yield of synthesized compounds. IR spectra of newly synthesized peptide derivatives showed characteristic Amide I and Amide II bands of the -CO-NH- moieties at 1668–1640 and 1539–1532 cm⁻¹ which clearly indicated the completeness of coupling reaction. This fact was further confirmed by the appearance of singlets at 8.55–6.25 and 175.2–168.6 ppm corresponding to -CO-NH- moiety in ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of compounds **1**₁₋₁₂. Presence of aldehydic group was indicated by medium to strong bands at 2825–2822, 2726–2717 and 1708–1702 cm⁻¹ in IR spectra of peptide derivatives. Further, presence of bands at 3298–2489 and 1719–1716 cm⁻¹ (for -C(=O)-OH moiety) in IR spectra and broad singlet at 10.05 ppm (for -COOH moiety) in ¹H NMR spectra of compounds **1**₁₀₋₁₂ and disappearance of strong bands at 1748 and 1269 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C=O and C-O moiety (ester) in IR spectra and singlets

Note

X = L-pro (1₁), L-tyr (1₂,1₁₀), L-ile (1₃), L-nitro(arg) (1₄), L-leu-L-pro (1₅), L-his-L-try (1₆,1₁₁), gly-gly (1₇), L-ser-L-leu-L-try (1₈), L-ala-L-pro-L-pro (1₉,1₁₂)

Scheme

at 52.7–52.3 and 3.56 ppm (for -OCH₃ moiety) in ¹³C and ¹H NMR spectra of compounds 1₂, 1₆ and 1₉ further confirmed the completion of hydrolysis reaction. Moreover, mass spectrum of ester and corresponding acid derivatives showed characteristic fragment ion peaks (M-31 and MeOCO⁺ - m/z 59) and (M-17, M-45 and COOH⁺ - m/z 45) along with respective molecular ion peak (M⁺) and elemental analysis afforded values (±0.03), consistent with molecular composition of synthesized compounds.

All the synthesized compounds were found to exhibit moderate to good antifungal activity against pathogenic fungi. Compounds 1₄, 1₆ and 1₁₁ displayed significant activity against pathogenic *C. albicans*, most potent compound being 1₁₁ (ZOI : 25 mm, MIC : 6 µg/ml) which displayed bioactivity even better than standard drug (ZOI : 20 mm, MIC : 6 µg/ml). Moreover, compound 1₉ (ZOI : 15–17 mm, MIC : 12.5 µg/ml) and its hydrolyzed derivative 1₁₂ (ZOI : 16–19 mm, MIC : 12.5 µg/ml) showed significant activity against dermatophytes, in comparison to reference compound - griseofulvin (ZOI : 17–20 mm, MIC : 12.5 µg/ml). Almost, all the synthesized com-

pounds possessed moderate activity against gram-negative bacteria, except compounds 1₄ and 1₈ (ZOI : 27–28 mm, MIC : 6 µg/ml) which displayed even better activity against *P. aeruginosa*, in comparison to standard drug - ciprofloxacin (ZOI : 25 mm, MIC : 6 µg/ml). No compound exhibited significant activity against gram-positive bacteria except moderate level of activity for compound 1₇ (ZOI : 14 mm, MIC : 12.5 µg/ml) against pathogenic *B. subtilis*. Analysis of anthelmintic activity data suggested that dipeptide analogs 1₅₋₇, 1₁₁ (MPT/MDT ratio - 9.19–19.52/14.25–33.52 min) possessed more activity in comparison to tripeptides 1_{8,9} and 1₁₂ (MPT/MDT ratio - 17.31–26.60/26.22–35.02 min) which in turn, exhibited more activity than amino acid derivatives 1₄ and 1₁₀ (MPT/MDT ratio - 24.11–40.21/35.40–55.52 min). Further, compounds 1₆ and 1₁₁ (MPT/MDT ratio - 9.19 – 14.22/19.50–23.41 min) showed better activity against all three earthworm species, in comparison to standard drug - mebendazole (MPT/MDT ratio - 13.42–17.52/22.58–29.54 min) and compound 1₅ (MPT/MDT ratio - 13.44–17.49/22.52–29.52 min) displayed anthelmintic activity comparable to reference drug. *Eudrilus* sp. was

found to be less sensitive towards the newly synthesized phenoxyacetic acid derivatives, in comparison to other two earthworm species. Comparison of biological activity data suggested that hydrolyzed peptide derivatives **1**₁₀₋₁₂ (MPT/MDT ratio – 9.19–33.09/14.25–47.52 min) displayed better activity in comparison to corresponding ester derivatives **1**₂, **1**₆ and **1**₉ (MPT/MDT ratio – 10.26–35.35/19.50–49.05 min). On passing toxicity tests, these compounds may prove good candidates for clinical studies and can be new antimicrobial and anthelmintic agents of future.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. L-Amino acids, di-*tert*-butylpyrocarbonate (Boc₂O), trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), DCC, TEA and NMM were obtained from Spectrochem Limited, Mumbai, India. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu 8700 Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer using a thin film supported on KBr pellets/CHCl₃ as solvent for the synthesized compounds. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AC NMR spectrometer (300 MHz) using CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol JMS DX 303 Mass spectrometer operating at 70 eV. Elemental analyses of all the compounds were performed on Elementar vario EL III. Purity of all the compounds was checked by TLC on precoated silica gel G plates.

Preparation of di/tripeptide methyl esters :

L-Amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride/dipeptide methyl ester (10 mmol) was coupled with Boc-L-amino acid (10 mmol) using DCC (2.1 g, 10 mmol) as coupling agent and TEA (2.9 ml, 21 mmol) as base according to the Bodanzky and Bodanzky procedure with certain modifications¹³ to get Boc-protected di/tripeptide methyl ester. The resulting ester (10 mmol) was dissolved in CHCl₃ (15 ml) and treated with TFA (2.28 g, 20 mmol) and solution was stirred at RT for 1 h, washed with saturated NaHCO₃ solution (25 ml). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by crystallization from CHCl₃ and petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60 °C) to get pure di/tripeptide methyl ester.

tert-Butyloxycarbonyl-L-seryl-L-leucyl-L-tryptophan methyl ester :

Semisolid mass; yield 77%; Found : C, 60.25; H, 7.36; N, 10.79. Calcd. for C₂₆H₃₈N₄O₇ (518) : C, 60.22; H, 7.39; N, 10.80%; ¹³C NMR : δ 176.2, 175.5, 173.0 (3C, -C=O, try, ser and leu), 157.5 (-C=O, boc), 137.2

(C-β', indole), 128.4 (C-γ', indole), 123.6 (C-ζ, indole), 122.9 (C-β, indole), 120.0, 119.2, 112.7 (3C, C-ε, C-δ and C-η, indole), 109.1 (C-γ, indole), 79.9 (C-α, boc), 63.6, 58.1 (2C, C-β and C-α, ser), 54.5 (C-α, try), 51.2 (OCH₃), 42.3, 39.1 (2C, C-α and C-β, leu), 28.8 (3C, C-β, boc), 27.9 (C-β, try), 25.5 (C-γ, leu), 21.7 (2C, C-δ, leu) ppm.

L-Seryl-L-leucyl-L-tryptophan methyl ester :

Semisolid mass; yield 82%; Found : C, 60.28; H, 7.25; N, 13.36. Calcd. for C₂₁H₃₀N₄O₅ (418) : C, 60.27; H, 7.23; N, 13.39%; ¹³C NMR : δ 176.7, 172.8, 169.5 (3C, -C=O, try, leu and ser), 137.6 (C-β', indole), 128.1 (C-γ', indole), 123.8 (C-ζ, indole), 122.8 (C-β, indole), 119.9, 118.7, 112.2 (3C, C-ε, C-δ and C-η, indole), 109.5 (C-γ, indole), 65.2, 59.3 (2C, C-β and C-α, ser), 55.0 (C-α, try), 51.6 (OCH₃), 49.8, 41.5 (2C, C-α and C-β, leu), 27.5 (C-β, try), 26.1 (C-γ, leu), 22.4 (2C, C-δ, leu) ppm.

tert-Butyloxycarbonyl-L-alanyl-L-prolyl-L-proline methyl ester :

Semisolid mass; yield 72%; Found : C, 57.38; H, 7.85; N, 10.60. Calcd. for C₁₉H₃₁N₃O₆ (397) : C, 57.42; H, 7.86; N, 10.57%; ¹H NMR : δ 6.42 (1H, br s, -NH), 4.50–4.47 (1H, t, H-α, pro-1), 4.45–4.37 (1H, m, H-α, ala), 4.25–4.25 (1H, t, H-α, pro-2), 3.72–3.67 (4H, m, H-δ, pro-1 and pro-2), 3.62 (3H, s, -OCH₃, ester), 2.72–2.67 (2H, q, H-β, pro-1), 2.05–1.99 (4H, m, H-β and H-γ, pro-2), 1.91–1.85 (2H, m, H-γ, pro-1), 1.63–1.61 (3H, d, *J* 5.85 Hz, H-β, ala), 1.55 (9H, s, butyl-*t*) ppm.

L-Alanyl-L-prolyl-L-proline methyl ester :

Semisolid mass; yield 69%; Found : C, 56.58; H, 7.79; N, 14.15. Calcd. for C₁₄H₂₃N₃O₄ (297) : C, 56.55; H, 7.80; N, 14.13%; ¹H NMR : δ 4.39–4.36 (1H, t, H-α, pro-1), 4.25–4.22 (1H, t, H-α, pro-2), 3.75–3.71 (2H, t, H-δ, pro-2), 3.62 (3H, s, -OCH₃, ester), 3.61–3.56 (1H, m, H-α, ala), 3.55–3.51 (2H, t, H-δ, pro-1), 2.74–2.69 (2H, q, H-β, pro-1), 2.09–2.02 (4H, m, H-β and H-γ, pro-2), 1.95 (2H, br s, -NH₂), 1.90–1.85 (2H, m, H-γ, pro-1), 1.13–1.11 (3H, d, *J* 5.9 Hz, H-β, ala) ppm.

Preparation of 2-(4-bromo-2-formyl-phenoxy)acetic acid (1) :

Sodium hydroxide (0.9 g, 22.4 mmol) was dissolved in water (25 ml) and resulting alkaline solution was slowly added to another solution of 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (2 g, 10 mmol) and chloroacetic acid (0.94 g, 10 mmol) in water (25 ml) with stirring. The reaction mixture was heated to remove all the liquid and the residue was treated with water (30 ml). The mixture was cooled, filtered and

acidified with dilute HCl. The aqueous layer was extracted with Et₂O (2 × 25 ml) and combined organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The crude product was crystallized from ethanol and water (1 : 1) to get pale yellow crystals of compound 1.

Preparation of 2-(4-bromo-2-formyl-phenoxy)acetyl amino acid and peptide esters (1₁₋₉) :

Compound 1 (2.6 g, 10 mmol) was dissolved in CHCl₃ (35 ml) and added to a mixture of L-amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride/deprotected dipeptide/tripeptide methyl ester (10 mmol) in CHCl₃ (35 ml) to which NMM (2.3 ml, 21 mmol) was previously added at 0 °C with stirring. To the above mixture, DCC (2.1 g, 10 mmol) was added and stirring was done for 36 h. The reaction mixture was filtered and filtrate was washed with 5% NaHCO₃ and saturated NaCl solutions (20 ml each). Organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ followed by evaporation in vacuum. Crude product was crystallized from a mixture of chloroform and n-hexane followed by cooling at 0 °C.

Preparation of 2-(4-bromo-2-formyl-phenoxy)acetyl amino acids and peptides (1₁₀₋₁₂) :

Compound 1₂/1₆/1₉ (10 mmol) was dissolved in THF : H₂O (1 : 1, 36 ml) and LiOH (0.36 g, 15 mmol) was added to above solution at 0 °C. The mixture was stirred at RT for 1 h and then acidified to pH 3.5 with 1 N H₂SO₄. The aqueous layer was extracted with Et₂O (3 × 15 ml). The combined organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. Crude product was crystallized from methanol and ether.

All synthesized compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity¹⁴ against four bacterial strains *B subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli* and three fungal strains *M. audouinii*, *T. mentagrophytes* and *C. albicans* at 25–6 µg/ml concentration. MIC values of test compounds were determined by tube dilution technique. The solvent DMSO was used as negative control and ciprofloxacin/griseofulvin were used as standards. Average diameters of the zones of inhibitions (ZOI, in mm) for test samples were calculated for triplicate sets. The diameters obtained for the test samples were compared with that produced by the standard drug. Anthelmintic activity studies¹⁵ were carried out against three different species of earthworms *M. konkanensis*, *P. corethruses* and *Eudrilus* sp. at 2 mg/ml concentration using Tween 80 (0.5%) in distilled water as control and mebendazole

as reference compound. The mean paralyzing and death times (MPT/MDT) were calculated for triplicate sets. The death time was ascertained by placing the earthworms in warm water (60 °C) which stimulated the movement, if the worm was alive

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